

Deliverable D1.5

Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities

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Change Log

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DMP	Data Management Plan
DX.X	Deliverable
EIC	European Innovation Council
ESB	Economic Supervision Board
ISB	Industrial Supervision Board
ME	Multiphoton Endoscopy
N	Nitrogen
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PPTX	file extension for a Microsoft PowerPoint Open XML Presentation file
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version

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Executive Summary

This report on the Dissemination and Communication Activities of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project provides guidance on presenting information to the project's various target audiences. It outlines templates for official documentation, proposed promotional materials, and a boilerplate text summarising the project's key aspects. The report also includes a general overview of the project's website, social media channels, and Zenodo repository, as previously discussed in Deliverable 1.1 'Project Logo, Website, and Social Media', and concludes with a brief reference to the measurement of impact through communication metrics.

1. Introduction

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is part of the European Innovation Council (EIC) through the Pathfinder Open Call and is led by the project coordinator, Euro-BioImaging ERIC. The consortium is a partnership of 8 beneficiaries, with representation from Austria, Italy, Finland, France, and the Netherlands. The project started on May 1st, 2025, and continues until April 2028.

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS seeks to transform agricultural practices through innovation in Digital Precision Agronomy. The primary objective of the project is to develop the first mobile imaging technology for in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops, thereby enabling more effective crop management practices.

The dissemination of results and outreach materials to the public requires a coherent and structured approach. This report on the Dissemination and Communication Activities for the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project provides a general framework for effectively sharing project developments with external audiences. It should be read in conjunction with Deliverable 1.1, which offers complementary information on the project website, as well as the social media and Zenodo channels.

2. Description of work

2.1. Stakeholders

The main stakeholders of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project are considered to be the following groups:

Stakeholder category	Definition
<i>Agrochemical/agronomic companies</i>	Industry players who can integrate precision fertiliser management with the project's outcomes
<i>Tracer Companies</i>	Industry players who are interested and involved in the multimodal tracer market
<i>RE-IMAGINE-CROPS partners</i>	Participants in the project who either provide services and infrastructure or are potential users of them.

<p><i>RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Consortium Bodies</i></p>	<p>There are three main Consortium bodies in the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project: <i>the Project Coordination</i>, <i>the Scientific Coordination</i> (both of whom are responsible for the overall and scientific aspects of the project), and <i>the Steering Committee</i> (the decision-making body of the consortium, comprising a representative from each partner). Moreover, the Industrial Supervision Board and the Economic Supervision Board are also considered consortium bodies, though their role is solely advisory.</p>
<p><i>Agricultural Research Institutes and Universities</i></p>	<p>Includes plant biology departments, crop science labs, and agricultural engineering programmes</p>
<p><i>General Public</i></p>	<p>Individuals outside the primary users that may be interested in the project outcomes, such as imaging and/or agricultural enthusiasts, readers of scientific journals, and media representatives</p>

2.2. Branding

As outlined in Deliverable 1.1, branding a project is key to its ease of recognition and dissemination of a coherent message. In addition to the assets described in the deliverable, the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project will have more assets at its disposal to facilitate communication with internal and external stakeholders.

2.2.1. Templates

Templates for presentations are available to all project partners, to maintain a consistent representation of the project branding. The following items are stored in the project's *Google Drive*:

- A presentation template: a slide deck providing an overview of the project (including the objective, goal, partners, and structure) is available in a PPTX format. Other versions of the slide decks, tailored to different specific audiences, will be developed throughout the course of the project.
- A one-slide project summary
- A letterhead document for official communications.
- An abstract describing the project.
- The deliverable template

The following pictures represent stills of the presentation template; they will be subject to change as the project progresses:

2.2.2. Promotional items

Potential merchandise items (flyers, mugs, tote bags, etc.) will be distributed at the events organised by RE-IMAGINE-CROPS, being mindful of the environmental impact that they could create. A couple of tentative options are shown below:

2.2.3. Boilerplate Text

A boilerplate text will be available on the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS website. The following is a tentative version:

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS is a Horizon Europe-funded project that brings together leading research institutions, imaging specialists, and agricultural industry partners to advance sustainable crop management. The project focuses on developing the first real-time, in-field portable multimodal multiscale imaging system that combines Positron Emission Tomography (PET) with Multiphoton Endoscopy (ME).

This integrated technology will enable precise, non-invasive measurements of plant responses to nitrogen (N) fertiliser at both metabolic and cellular levels directly in the field. By linking imaging data with plant physiological processes, the project will support the development of optimised fertilisation strategies that reduce ecological impact and improve resource efficiency.

The goal of RE-IMAGINE-CROPS is to tailor fertiliser application by measuring functional processes that reflect the crop's local and systemic responses shortly after nitrogen delivery. Through this approach, the project aims to contribute to more sustainable and data-driven agricultural practices.

The consortium includes eight partner institutions: *Euro-BioImaging ERIC* (coordination), *BF Educational*, *University of Turku*, *University of Maastricht*, *CNRS* in connection with the *University of Lille*, *LIGHTCORE Technologies*, *VRVis*, and *University of Teramo*; combining expertise in plant science, bioimaging, modelling, and agri-food innovation to ensure both scientific excellence and real-world impact.

2.2.4. Key messages

<p>Objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop, prove, and exploit the commercialisation of a novel real-time RE-IMAGINE-CROPS technology for the in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops • Develop, prove, and exploit the commercialisation of a novel crop management method based on the real-time RE-IMAGINE-CROPS technology for agronomists, scientists and the fertilisers industry
<p>Motivation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an innovative imaging technology to support more sustainable and efficient crop management, addressing one of agriculture's most

	pressing challenges: the overuse of nitrogen (N) fertilisers.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a mobile prototype integrating PET and endoscopy imaging technologies • Design AI-based software for co-registration of multiscale, multimodal images • Conduct field testing to establish proof-of-concept of the technology
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A functional mobile prototype integrating PET and endoscopy imaging technologies • AI-driven software enabling accurate co-registration of multiscale, multimodal images • Multi-omics and phenotypic datasets supporting the interpretation of imaging outputs • Validated proof-of-concept demonstrated through rigorous field testing

2.3. Dissemination

2.3.1. Supervision Boards

The Impact and Long Vision Office, a newly established item within the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project, will be led by the partner BF Educational. It will oversee the creation of two supervisory boards with distinct mandates: (i) the Industrial Supervision Board (ISB), responsible for guiding the long-term vision and industrial relevance of project activities; and (ii) the Economic Supervision Board (ESB), tasked with assessing the project's economic impact and steering dissemination and communication efforts towards key stakeholders.

The selection of candidates for both boards will be coordinated by the Chair of the Impact and Long Vision Office, under the leadership of the partner BF Educational. In addition, the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board will contribute candidate proposals to ensure strong industry engagement.

2.3.2. Website and Social Media

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS website (re-imagine-crops.eurobioimaging.eu) serves as the primary source of information for all stakeholders of the project and all interested members of the general audience. The project website will be continuously updated throughout the duration of the project and will feature news, updates, and other relevant information related to the project's development.

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project already has social media handles on LinkedIn and Bluesky. While the current level of activity on these platforms is limited, a more consistent and targeted communication strategy will be implemented as soon as significant project results become available and suitable for dissemination to the general public. More information on the website and the Social Media channels has been shared in Deliverable 1.1.

2.3.3. Publications and Zenodo

Publications are a key aspect of communicating scientific research. We expect to publish multiple articles in high-impact international journals. The project has established a dedicated repository on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/re-imagine-crops/records>), which is linked to the Euro-BioImaging Research Organisation Registry profile. As outlined in Deliverable 1.1, all public deliverables and materials will be published in this account.

To acknowledge the funding, publications will use the following statement:

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101187260.

2.3.4. Events

In-person events for the dissemination of project activities and results will be organised throughout the duration of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project. Annual "RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Weeks" are planned to take place at the end of each project year to bring partners together and highlight key developments. Additionally, the Euro-BioImaging Expert Group in Plant Imaging, which meets monthly, will offer a platform to share project results through the Euro-BioImaging community. A dedicated European Symposium on "In-Field Imaging in Agriculture" is also anticipated around Month 30 of the project (October 2027). General details about the events are shared in the following table:

#	Main Networking, Communication and Dissemination Events	Responsible Partner, Location	Expected Month (Date)	Action
1	RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Week 1: Industrial and Scientific meeting "Precision Agronomy: present and needs"	BF Educational, Italy	11 (March 2026)	

2	RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Week 2: Industrial and Scientific meeting “Optical Imaging Technologies for Precision Agronomy”	LIGHTCORE, France	23 (March 2027)
3	RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Week 3: Industrial and Scientific meeting “Data Analysis Methods for Precision Agronomy”	BF Educational, Italy	35 (March 2028)
4	Euro-Biolmaging Expert Group in Plant Imaging	Euro-Biolmaging, Online	Monthly
5	European Symposium on “In-Field” Imaging in Agriculture	Euro-Biolmaging, Finland	30 (October 2027)

2.3.5. Communications Impact Measurement

All Work Packages are responsible for contributing to the dissemination and exploitation of the project’s outcomes. Metrics from the project’s communication channels—including social media platforms (LinkedIn, Bluesky) and the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS website—will be collected and analysed to assess outreach and engagement. Website analytics will be facilitated through WordPress, which enables the systematic tracking and analysis of visitor activity, content performance, and user engagement trends. Additionally, dissemination and communication activities of the project members will be collected and tracked through a project dissemination registry.

3. Conclusion

The Dissemination and Communication Activities deliverable outlines the strategy for engaging with stakeholders and the general public. It serves as a reference structure for the consortium to disseminate the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project results and raise awareness in a consistent and coordinated manner across various target audiences.

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